

TRADITION AND MODERNITY: THOUGHTS ON *BUNTFU* IN EMBHIKHWAKHE COMMUNITY, ESWATINI

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ABSTRACT

Tradition and modernity are two concepts that can be used to best describe the way of living in Eswatini. The traditional Emaswati believe and also practise their different cultures. The modern Emaswati are living like their former colonizers. According to the community elders, there is a clash between the traditional way of life and the modern way of living. The aim of this article is to explain how Emaswati use buntfu as a notion of African social justice in the treatment of women and children, and the socialisation of boys and girls into adulthood. Qualitative research and focus group interviews were conducted. Purposive sampling was used to sample the research participants. Ubuntu as a moral theory was used to ground the study. The findings indicate that amongst the Emaswati, buntfu is regarded as a way of life; as a core identity of individual being. Buntfu is also associated with the values of respect, while some have suggested that buntfu is a nostalgic yearning for the “golden past”.

Keywords: Culture, *incwala*, tradition, modernity, *buntfu*.

INTRODUCTION

Historically, Swaziland (now called Eswatini) was colonised by the British from 1906 to 1968. As a result, Swaziland is influenced by both traditional nationalistic identity and modern British influence (Pejstrup, 2011). The Emaswati regard themselves as a culturally oriented nation that continues to practice traditions such as *buntfu*. Eswatini is the only country that is ruled by a monarch (Daly, 2001) in the African sub-Saharan region. Modernity is “an illusion of development and a tradition that sometimes reflects a poor image of a mythical past” (Mudimbe, 1988: 5). Mudimbe (1988) defines modernity as a marginal space where people lose their cultural identity and follow the ways of thinking and doing things of the so-called modernised societies. In this case, the modernised society is Britain. Modernisation simply means to remould a cultural system into a new mode (Hirai, 1993: 4). The new culture that emerged as a result of remoulding is characterised by the introduction of telephones, television sets (TVs), aeroplanes, mass communication, bureaucratic institutions, and computer control systems (Hirai, 1993: 4). “Modernisation is widely viewed as a uniquely western process that non-western societies follow by deserting their traditional cultures and embracing technologically and morally superior western ways” (Baker, 2000: 19) of life. During the process of modernisation, non-Western countries such as Swaziland do away with their traditional ways of life; for example, they stop staying in separate huts and cooking at *emagumeni* (*liguma* is a place where cooking and preparation of food in Swazi households are done). (*Emaguma* is

plural for *liguma*; *emagumeni* is, therefore, an adjective for the word *liguma*.) The origin of the word “tradition” directs to the process of transmission, delivery and maintenance of values, properties, customs, and principles, which marks the cultural identity of individuals, groups, nations, and mankind (Petković, 2007: 24). Therefore, when we talk about the traditional way of life or traditional culture of the Swazis, we are referring to “all human activities such as religion, philosophy, moral, standards, laws, politics economic, society, history, literature, and art that has been preserved, learned and transmitted in a given community or group over a long period of time” (Hirai, 1993: 1).

It is imperative to define the concept of “culture” in this article. Culture can therefore be described as “a system of knowledge, beliefs, procedures, attitudes, and artifacts that are shared within a group (of people)” (Gill, 2013: 71). “A cultural argument emphasizes how behaviour is the result of beliefs, shared in a group-by-group members and brought about usually through socialization within family or community” (Schnittker, 2013: 92). In the traditional culture, sharing of beliefs among the same members of the family or community is key. Some researchers such as Zhongyun (1987: 443) define culture from a different perspective. Zhongyun’s description even encapsulates the spirituality of the people. According to Zhongyun (1987: 443), “culture in its broad sense implies both materials, spiritual civilisation including ways of life, ways of thinking, social customs, generally accepted criteria for behaviour as perceived by the man in the street”. Zhongyun (1987), Petkovic (2007) and Hirai (1993) have a common agreement that culture and traditional values are shared from generation to generation.

Amongst the Emaswati, *buntfu* is not merely about positive human qualities. Instead, it is the very essence of humanity. Hence the general view that human beings or “*bantfu*” or humanised beings live in daily self-expressive works of love and efforts to create harmonious relationships in the community and the world beyond (Mnyandu, 1997: 81). According to Chirongoma, Manda and Myeni (2008: 195), “the emphasis that *buntfu* places on relations emerges from the interaction between the community and the individual”. This sense of communal interdependence can also be found in the work of Kenyan theologian and philosopher, John S. Mbiti (1989: 109), who coins the maxim: “I am because we are; and since we are, therefore I am”. For Kenyatta (1965: 296), “according to Kikuyu ways of thinking, nobody is an isolated individual”. For Verhoef and Michel (1997: 396), the “we” of the African ethos “is a shared experience. People are closely interconnected with one another in a lifestyle-oriented to the “other”. Thus, the individual is no longer an “I” for myself but becomes the “I” in the community for others. The word “*buntfu*” in simple terms means “humanity” or “being human” (Chirongoma *et al.*, 2008: 194). In Swazi culture, *buntfu* can also be regarded as the value of humanness (Broodryk, 2002). We should hasten to mention that the notion of *buntfu* is widely used among the Bantu-speaking people of Southern Africa. Letseka (2017: 3) cites Tambulasi and Kayuni (2005: 148), who show that in the Chewa language of Zambia, *buntfu* is known as *umunthu*; amongst the Yao speakers of Malawi, *buntfu* is referred to as *umundu*;

amongst the Tsonga people in South Africa, Mozambique, Zimbabwe and Swaziland, *buntfu* is known as *bunhu*. Amongst the Shona people in Zimbabwe, it is *unhu*, while amongst the Sotho-speaking people of Lesotho, Botswana and South Africa, *buntfu* is known as *botho*, and amongst the Venda speakers of South Africa, it is known as *vhutu*.

Twenty-first century globalisation has introduced complex cultural interconnections between diverse locations (Syed, 2013: 647). Through information and communication technologies (ICTs), different global cultures have become easily accessible. Technology and media occupy centre stage in the transmission and creation of new global cultures for the 21st century, which are believed to stand in opposition to traditional Swazi customs and traditions. In Eswatini, in the era of the internet and online resources, modern electronic devices such as smartphones and tablets, as well as television (TV) are regarded by the elders as the drivers of perceived undesirable behaviour amongst the young people of Eswatini.

According to Pejstrup (2011), the world around Emaswati is changing drastically. However, traditionalists and those who see themselves as the custodians of Emaswati traditions and cultures are reluctant to embrace the change that comes with modernisation. As Mdluli (2009: 63) observes:

The Swazi nation is known worldwide for holding onto its cultural values, traditional practices, and customary beliefs. It is not surprising that the individual Swazi traditionalist is still keen to see the traditional norms and values observed in the community. To some extent, Westernization has affected the traditional lifestyle but not in its entirety.

It should be mentioned that Emaswati cultures are not sufficiently documented. Instead, they are passed from one generation to another by word of mouth. Cultures in Eswatini play a pivotal role in influencing behaviour among the Emaswati people, at home, in various communities, or anywhere in the world wherever they might be. There is a tendency for those who consider themselves knowledgeable in Emaswati cultures to portray their perspectives as objective, that is as if they are representative of their respective communities or the larger Eswatini nation. Some might question this tendency given that Swazi oral traditions provide several avenues of useful information for historians and archaeologists alike (Perry, 1991). This article is divided into five sections. First, we sketch the notion of *buntfu*. Second, we describe the methodology used to gather the data. Third, we discuss the findings. Then, we highlight emergent trends and key themes. Finally, we offer some concluding remarks. Additionally, we shall acknowledge some of the research participants who passed away before and after fieldwork.

THE NOTION OF *BUNTFU*

The notion of *buntfu* has been widely delineated in Southern Africa (Broodryk, 2002; Letseka, 2012, 2000; Metz and Gaie, 2010; Metz, 2007; Mokgoro, 1998;

Ramose, 2002, 1999; Shutte, 1994; Tutu, 1999). For instance, Letseka (2000: 180) argues that *buntfu* should be regarded as “a normative concept that encapsulates moral values such as altruism, kindness, generosity, compassion, benevolence, courtesy, and respect and concern for others”. Broodryk (2002) regards *buntfu* as a comprehensive ancient African worldview based on the values of humanness, caring, sharing, respect, compassion, and associated values. Ramose (2002: 270) conceived of *buntfu* as being human (humanness); a humane, respectful and polite attitude towards others; *buntfu* is the root of African philosophy. The being of an African in the universe is inseparably anchored upon *buntfu*. It is Ramose’s (2002: 230) contention that *buntfu* is the wellspring flowing with African ontology and epistemology. He argues that a persuasive philosophical argument can be made that there is a “family atmosphere” – a kind of philosophical affinity and kinship among and between the indigenous people of Africa, which is captured in the maxim: *umuntu ngumuntu ngabantu*, of which the English translation approximates something like: “a person is a person through other persons”. A siSwati version is *umuntfu ngu-muntfu ngebantfu*. The Zulus and the Xhosas say *umuntu ngumuntu ngabantu* (Khoza, 2006: 6; Msila, 2015: 5), while the Sotho-speaking people say *motho ke motho ka batho* (Letseka, 2012: 2000). The maxims speak to the emphasis on communality and interdependence of the members of an African community (Letseka, 2012). The English approximation of *ubuntu ngu muntfu ngebantfu* is “a person is a person through others”. This implies that because we share in a common human condition, we also recognise our commonality by being humble, compassionate, and tolerant towards others. Thus, the concept of *buntfu* embodies an understanding of what it means to be human and what is necessary for human beings to grow and find fulfilment in life (Khomba, 2011; Shutte, 2001; Khoza, 2006). We can therefore argue that *buntfu* places the emphasis on communality and interdependence.

As Waghid and Davids (2014) point out, the notion of *buntfu* is constitutive of African political, social, and ethical thought, often illuminating the communal interdependence of persons geared towards the cultivation of human flourishing in indigenous African societies – a body of collective experience, an understanding that one’s experiences are never entirely one’s own. As Tutu (2004: 25) aptly points out, none of us comes into the world fully formed. We would not know how to think, walk, speak, or behave as human beings unless we learned from other human beings. We need other human beings in order to be human. Thus, *buntfu* can be reasonably described as the capacity in African culture to express compassion, reciprocity, dignity, humanity, and mutuality in the interests of the building and maintaining communities with justice and mutual caring (Khoza, 2006; Mandela, 1995; Tutu, 1999).

As Lauras-Lecoh (1990: 480) observes: “Worldwide Africa is seen as one of the sanctuaries of the extended family. It is the continent where the nuclear family, reduced to a couple and their offspring, is still a rarity.” In the same vein, Gyekye (1997: 292) posits that “one outstanding cultural value of the traditional African society that is a feature of ever-present consciousness of ties of kinship on the

importance of the family (is) the extended family". For Mbiti (1975: 176), the extended family is a microcosm of the wider society. It embodies a broad spectrum of personal associations between great-grandparents, grandparents, fathers, mothers, uncles, aunts, children (sisters, brothers, cousins, nephews and nieces), a host of maternal and paternal relatives, as well as the departed members. For Ayisi (1992: 16), the extended family forms the *raison d'être* of all social co-operation and responsibility. In another publication, Mbiti (1989: 106) argues that in African communal life, "the individual cannot exist alone except corporately. She owes her existence to other people, including those of past generations and her contemporaries".

UBUNTU AS A MORAL THEORY

Metz (2011) defines *ubuntu* from a Western perspective. Mertz (2011: 532) uses three ideas to disqualify the value of using the notion of *ubuntu* in a society or country. His assumptions are focused on the South African community. Mertz (2011) argues that *ubuntu* is deemed to be an inappropriate basis for public morality in today's South Africa because it is too vague, it fails to acknowledge the value of individual freedom, and, thirdly it fits a traditional, small-scale culture more than modern, industrial society. *Ubuntu* is difficult to pin down to one meaning or a series of meanings owing to its dynamic nature (Metz, 2007: 323). *Ubuntu* has been the subject of continuous, intense debate among academics and courts alike (Radebe and Phooko, 2017: 239). Western countries have their own ways and views of describing their cultures and those foreign to them; they often use lenses such as modernity and the technology era as their basis of argument. African countries base their morals or morality on their traditional cultures which are unwritten but are passed down from one generation to the other by word of mouth. Metz has a different view about the concept *buntfu* and the way it is being used in South Africa or African countries for that matter. Although his description fits well in the European way of seeing the world, it is not representative of how a black South African understands and views *buntfu*. Additionally, his understanding of *buntfu* does not resonate with literature from most of the African literature about *buntfu* (Mudimbe, 1988; Gyekye, 1997; Ramose, 2007; Letseka, 2012; Msila, 2015).

The way black South Africans view *buntfu* can be different, which is not necessarily similar to the "we"; therefore, they argue that *ubuntu* as a moral theory is relevant and it is still critical for African countries. Morality is cross-cultural (Metz, 2007: 332). However, we cannot run away from the notion that different people look at morality from different perspectives, which are informed mostly by their own traditional cultures. According to the elders, the African traditional cultures should not be treated as a homogeneous culture. We, however, agree that the concept of "morality" in *ubuntu* is mainly about the morality of individuals, and how they carry themselves as individuals and as a group. *Ubuntu* as a moral theory should be treated as African ethical thinking, which is not similar to that of Western ethical thinking (Ramose, 2007). It is illusory to define *ubuntu* as a moral theory or African morality using cultural universals which have previously

marginalised the African people because there is an incompatibility between universalism and particularism (Wiredu, 1996: 1). Wiredu (1996: 68) clarifies further that the problem is thinking that morals are independent of anything human but assuming that morality is only correctly conceived from a divine suitably Olympian perspective. We equate the Olympian perspective to the superior point of view when compared to any human. The *ubuntu* moral theory has enabled us to explicitly define the concept of *ubuntu*, and also analyse the data collected in this article about how *ubuntu* was used as a moral law amongst the people of Swaziland. Using this theory helped the researchers to understand that the concepts of tradition and modernity are also interlinked to the superior perspective of defining morals from a divine Olympian perspective, whereby modernity is seen “as an illusion of development and tradition reflects a poor image of a mythical past” (Mudimbe, 1988: 5).

RESEARCH METHOD

A qualitative research method was used in this study. Case studies and focus group interviews that involved oral historical conversations were used to collect data at Embhikwakhe Inkhundla, Manzini District, Swaziland. Data was recorded on a device and it was later transcribed and translated from siSwati to English. A transcriber was hired to translate the conversations from siSwati to English. A total of eleven elders participated in the focus group interviews, which lasted for three to four hours for three days. The advantage of using focus group interviews is that the research participants were able to remind each other (Creswell, 2013) about any question that was posed to them. A good example is when we asked them where exactly the *intsanga* (a room for girls) was built or located in a Swazi homestead, and why. Letters of seeking permission were sent to the Embhikwakhe *Inkhundla*. *Tinkhundla* is a traditional system of governance in Swaziland (Simelane, 2017). *Tinkhundla* is plural. *Inkhundla* is a singular for *tinkhundla* (Simelane, 2017). Political parties are not allowed in Swaziland (Masuku and Limb, 2016). A gatekeeper was nominated, and he arranged for the research meetings to take place. One prince was also part of the research participants. All interviews were audio-taped to “remedy common, everyday memory problems” (Vemuri, Schmandt, Bender, Tellex and Lassey, 2004).

Purposive sampling was used to select the research participants. Purposive sampling is defined as “a form of non-probability sampling in which decisions concerning the individuals to be included in the sample are taken by the researcher, based upon a variety of criteria which may include specialist knowledge of the research issue, or capacity and willingness to participate in the research” (Oliver, 2006: 244). Saumure and Given (2008: 562) argue that “purposive sampling refers to a process where participants are selected because they meet criteria that have been predetermined by the researcher as relevant to addressing the research question (e.g. people of a particular age or another demographic category)”. In the same vein, for Patton (2002: 230), the logic and power of purposive sampling “lies in selecting information-rich cases whose study will illuminate the question under study”. It is Patton’s (2002: 246) view that “in

purposive sampling, the size of the sample is determined by informational considerations". For our purpose, the choice of purposive sampling was necessitated by the fact that not many community elders at the time of the interviews were alive or in a healthy state to contribute meaningfully to the conversations. Additionally, since the *incwala* traditional ceremony was taking place in Swaziland at the Royal Palace, elders were asked to meet at a convenient place at the same time. During the interviews, the researchers were accompanied by the gatekeeper, who is also actively involved at Embhikwakhe Inkhundla. Each visit was scheduled for a day. The day started with informal introductions and reminiscences between the elders about their upbringing. One of the participants was a prince to the late King Sobhuza's eleven sons.

Thus, the research participants were selected based on their old age and as knowledgeable of the Swaziland cultures, traditions, and customs. The interviews lasted for three to four hours. Focus group interviews were deemed suitable and appropriate given that the time the research team was granted access by the elders coincided with the *incwala* ceremony. During the *incwala* ceremony, individuals are not supposed to be seen holding their own gatherings, especially when the king or *iNgwenyama* (the lion) has summoned the nation to the Royal cattle kraal (*Eludzidzini*) for the *incwala* ceremony. A transcriber was hired to translate the conversations from siSwati to English. Two questions guided this research article. The questions were: "How did you use *buntfu* as a notion of African social justice in the treatment of women and children?" and "Explain how *buntfu* as a pedagogical principle was used in socialising boys and girls into adulthood."

A total of eleven community elders participated in this study. There were six men and five women. The research participants' ages ranged between 60 and 90 years. The age of 60 years and above was used as an inclusion criterion, and below 60 years was used as an exclusion criterion for the research participants. Canadian philosopher of education Egan (1992: 641) argues that "oral cultures place significant emphasis on memory to preserve knowledge, lore, and customs". In the same vein, Mandela (1995: 24) argues that the elders (or the *izikhulu*) "were wise men who retained the knowledge of tribal history and custom in their heads and whose opinions carried great weight". For Ayisi (1992: 69), "the elders are usually the oldest men in the society and constitute a gerontocratic core of the political structure". Consent forms were signed by the participants after the researchers had read them their rights of participating in the study. The researchers informed them that they have a right to not respond to questions they are uncomfortable answering and that they were not going to be punished or penalised in any way. We should mention that all the research participants were active members of the Embhikwakhe Inkhundla (Council).

Vansina (2006) argues that oral traditions are the main available source for the construction of the past, and even those among people who have written many historical sources, including the most ancient ones, are based on oral traditions. Vansina (1985: 197) further argues that:

The genres of oral tradition in oral societies are as diverse as those of documents in a literate one. Their contents range over all aspects of human activity from demographic data to various sorts of data about art. Their range is wider than that of documents in most literate societies and includes the evidence that oral history there unearths.

RESEARCH FINDINGS

The researchers followed Creswell's (2013: 179) and Creswell and Poth's (2016: 44) ideas of data analysis and presentation. Data analysis used both inductive and deductive approaches (Creswell, 2013: 44). Using the inductive and deductive approaches enabled the researchers to work back and forth in-between data. The researchers started by reviewing and making sense of the data (Creswell and Poth, 2016: 44). Data coding and forming patterns resulted in the forming of themes (Creswell, 2013; Creswell and Poth, 2016). Five major findings emerged from the data of this study: humility and respect are *buntfu*, television promotes modern and foreign cultures and the educated way traditions are looked down upon; boys and girls are socialised differently; absence of grandparents exacerbates a lack of *buntfu*, and gay and lesbian relationships are taboo in the Swazi culture.

The question on how *buntfu* as a notion of African social justice was used in the treatment of women and children yielded the following responses:

Humility and respect are *buntfu*

"You will notice that the practice of having a girls' hut on one side and that of the boys on the other side is no longer practiced. For example, picture a scenario whereby a man is reading the news article inside the big house and there comes a child walking stark naked. Wow! You will see the paper falling and now you look, ah! This one is like this: the sexual feelings do not care whether that child is my child or my sister's. This is what the Swazis were running away from; that you as the father of the children, do not enter into the *intsanga* of the maidens if you stand outside. You call out, "hey so and so!" And the mother too does not enter into the *lilawu* of the young men if she is outside. This is, therefore, one other thing that contributes to the wrongs that are happening now." (He was referring to the sexual assault of children.) (Respondent B).

"Yes, you bring up a child as a female or male. You bring him/her up teaching him/her humility..." (Respondent A).

"When we say a person is humane we see her/him by respect. It is respect that leads. Every time when she/he sees someone else he/she greets." (Respondent D).

Another responded replied as follows about "respect":

“...there was so much respect in the olden days...” and “there was some respect of knowing the social structures as to if there is someone who gives you hard time, you knew where to report him.” (Respondent E).

Television promotes modern and foreign cultures and the educated way traditions are looked down upon

“Television is not good. It is transmitting foreign cultures into our children’s lives. Our children are imitating what is happening on TV and they think they are living a modern life/*simanjemanje*. Now you find girls in love with each other and boys in love with other. This is an abomination. We never had this in our culture.” (Respondent E).

“...in short, the nationality that we grew up in, in the beginning, is now lost, it has shifted from us. We have got into foreigners’ way of living. King Sobhuza II said we should only take what is good from the white people but now we have taken everything, and we are using it. Today we say a wife is equal to a husband; 50/50.” (Respondent C).

“...What has caused this problem is the issue of being educated and the mixed social lives. The traditional setting is then considered an outdated thing... that is where respect ended. People have learned to have sex with their children...” (Respondent J).

Two themes emerged from this question: Humility and respect are *buntfu* and television promotes modern and foreign cultures and the educated way traditions are looked down upon. Most respondents mentioned that because *buntfu* promotes humility and respect, it was not expected for Emaswati men to ill-treat their women and children. Having sex with a child whether is a biological child or not is unheard of amongst Emaswati. It has been brought by the traditional modern way of living and the shortages of elderly people in families or communities. This is also a contributing factor to the erosion of the traditional Swati culture.

A question about socialisation of boys and girls yielded the following responses:

Boys and girls are socialised differently

Boys and girls are socialised differently amongst Emaswati. Grandfathers/men socialise the boy child. Grandmother/mothers socialize the girl child. (Respondent H).

Socialisation of girls into adolescents is a responsibility of the mother or grandmother...us, fathers have nothing to do with it. We only end with the boys. (Respondent G).

“...you will have sex with your man once you are married ...” (Respondent K).

“...let me add by saying that with regard to us males, we were given a lustful eye. Every male has lustful eyes for females. There are females who lust for males but, they are a few. You find that a woman will go out to propose to a man or another woman. You just note that she was so unlucky to be given lustful eyes. But with us in our Emaswati set-up it was noted that we have lustful eyes. That is why we, therefore, have *emalawu* (hut for boys) and *emaguma* (the place where women cook), and *tibuya* (kraal). We do not mix in the family. Even when the girls take the young men's food to *elawini*, they take it there whilst the young men are out. They will take the food to the *elawini*, and boys will come and eat after she has left so that they will not be able to talk to her.” (Respondent B).

“...Girls are supposed to be taught by the women because they need to teach them that they are also not supposed to touch the boys because they (girls) also have sexual feelings...” (Respondent J).

“...You should never have sex with a woman even if you are in love with her. There is a time for playing around in the thighs. Ey! Indeed you do not reach the vagina...”. (Respondent K).

“...when we were growing up, girl children were your sisters even those that were just staying in your home even if they were your cousins, they were as good as your sisters. You would not talk to them about getting to have sex with them, you respected them...” (Respondent L).

Gay and lesbian relationships are taboo in the Eswatini culture

“Television is not good. It is transmitting foreign cultures into our children's lives. Our children are imitating what is happening on TV and they think they are living a modern life/*simanjemanje*. Now you find girls in love with each (lesbian) other and boys in love with other (homosexual). This is an abomination. We never had this in our culture.” (Respondent E).

“...in short, our nationality that we grew up in, in the beginning, is now lost, it has shifted from us. We have got into foreigners' way of living. King Sobhuza II said we should only take what is good from the white people but now we have taken everything and we are using it. Today we say a wife is equal to a husband; 50/50.” (Respondent C).

An absence of grandparents exacerbates a lack of *buntf*

“Just to add ... because there are no more grandmothers, they are all back home. They grow up in rented houses and all the old people are back home. The children only go there when schools are closed. What is worse is that they live with all these kinds of people, and they learn all the bad habits that are there.” (Respondent I).

Data analysis on the question of how boys and girls were socialised resulted in the following themes: Girls and boys are socialised differently. (Men such as grandfathers or fathers are responsible for the socialising of boys. Women, for example, the grandmother or mother, are responsible for socialising girls.). Gay

and lesbian relationships are taboo in the Emaswati culture. The absence of grandparents exacerbates a lack of *buntfu*. Children of Emaswati are taught about good behaviour, respect, *buntfu*, and humility from an early age. Boys are expected to respect any girl and treat them as if they are from the same family, even those from extended families, villages and strangers. Having sex before marriage is taboo. Girls and boys who were unable to control their sexual desires were taught how to use a safe sex style or position that will prevent them from falling pregnant before marriage. The traditional stories that were told by grandparents which were passed from generation to generation were critical in building the character of a child and also socialising them in their culture and belief system.

CONCLUSION

Emaswati socialise boys and girls differently. Boys and girls are also expected to perform different household chores. The father or grandfather is responsible for socialising the boy child. Mothers and grandmothers are responsible for socialising the girl child. The lifestyle of people Eswatini is mainly influenced by tradition and their modern lifestyle (Mdluli, 2009; Pejstrup, 2011). The elders who participated in this research blamed television for transmitting foreign cultures, which are in conflict with the Eswatini way of life. Also, the educated Swazis and those living in urban and metropolitan cities and practicing global cultures were accused of looking down upon the Swazi cultures and traditions. Modernity is blamed for the current behaviour of Swazi boys and girls. Lack of elderly people such as grandmothers and grandfathers at home was seen as the major challenge as far as socialising of boys and girls is concerned.

Education, modernisation, television and urbanisation were seen as the contributing factors in the current behaviour of the Swazis and the erosion of the Swazi culture. Sex before marriage is regarded as taboo amongst the Swazi people. Children are taught before they reach the adolescent stage about how to behave and preserve themselves for marriage. The research data view the concerns of the participants as a longing for the traditional African society that is a feature of the ever-present consciousness of ties of kinship on the importance of the family the extended family (Gyekye, 1997: 292). The elders seem not to understand that Swaziland is living in a global world where global cultures or new cultures emerged as a result of remoulding, which is characterised by the introduction of telephones, television sets (TVs), aeroplanes, mass communication, bureaucratic institutions and computer control systems (Hirai, 1993: 4).

RECOMMENDATIONS

There is a need to do a bigger study that can include different voices and opinions of different Eswatini people about the use of *buntfu* as a notion of African social justice in the treatment of women and children. Another study can focus on how *buntfu* can be used to socialise boys and girls according to the Swazi culture, which should include the voices of the elders, boys, and girls.

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